

Pre-print

Exploring future land-use scenarios: Co-creation of a conceptual and quantitative model for Zambia

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Highlights

- Exploration of strategies to reduce deforestation, whilst meeting cooking, forestry, and food targets
- Co-creation with Local Experts of a conceptual model for land transitions in Zambia
- Co-development of "LandFutures_Zambia", a quantitative tool to explore land transitions
- Facilitate dialogue between decision-makers on trade-offs and uncertainties in policy objectives

Abstract

Understanding land-use transitions and their drivers is critical for policy makers and planners across the world. In Zambia, development ambitions including improving food security, increasing agricultural economic value, rapidly increasing mining and manufacturing biofuels all require land. Key questions surround how they can be achieved synergistically and sustainably, while stemming forest and other ecosystem degradation. Based on a co-creation process with local expert stakeholders, we mapped drivers and interconnections between land-use transitions, developed narratives for the land implications of alternative socio-economic development scenarios, and built a tool for exploring future land scenarios. We present a conceptual model of land-use change in Zambia, and the quantitative model "*LandFutures_Zambia*". This Excel-based tool projects the evolution of land-use and land cover under the expansion of settlement and cropland, tree harvesting for charcoal and restoration of degraded areas, thereby allowing users to explore alternative strategies for reducing land-cover change, especially deforestation, through interventions in the cooking, forestry and agriculture sectors. Both the conceptual model and Excel based tool are available for further application and development. These serve as a method to facilitate dialogue between decision-makers to explore uncertainties and trade-offs between policy objectives and interventions, including for estimation of greenhouse gas emissions.

1 Introduction

Global land-use change

Land-use change has affected almost a third of global land area since 1960 (Winkler et al., 2021). As populations grow and economies develop, demands for space and materials are rapidly increasing. Agriculture, urbanization and resource extraction are transforming natural landscapes, leading to major damage to ecosystems, soil, water and biodiversity (Hasan et al., 2020). Climate change is a driver of land-use change (LUC) as well as an effect (IPCC, 2019). With impacts on food security and conflicts being increasingly documented (e.g. Bununu et al., 2023; de Jong et al., 2021), it is clear that to tackle major social and environmental challenges it is vital to understand land-use change processes, drivers and potential mitigating interventions at local and larger scales.

Land-use change in Zambia

In recent decades, Zambia has experienced one of the highest rates of deforestation in the world (Vinya et al., 2011; Phiri et al., 2019), with major drivers being the clearance of forest for agricultural expansion, production of charcoal and expansion of settlements (Chomba et al., 2012). Land is key to sustainable development and land-cover change will undoubtedly continue. Settlements, food and fuel production must increase to meet the demands of a rapidly growing population, and Zambia's national development plans state ambitious goals for expanding mining activities, energy technologies, and other infrastructure (GRZ, 2006, 2022a).

The majority of the Zambian population (60%) relies on agriculture for their livelihoods (ZamStats, 2022). Much governmental effort focuses on supporting smallholder farmers to improve yields and increase their resilience to climate change impacts through the adoption of climate smart agricultural techniques (CIF, 2024). To increase adoption of climate-smart agriculture (CSA) techniques, government has introduced the Sustainable Agriculture Financing Facility (SAFF) for smallholder and emergent farmers to access irrigation equipment and other farming inputs with low interest loans (GRZ MoA, n.d.). There are also initiatives to reverse land degradation, regenerate degraded forests and develop community forest management programs (GRZ, 2019), with carbon markets offering new sources of funding (GRZ, 2023a; World Bank, 2024).

However, several challenges relate to both policy coherence and implementation (Kalaba et al., 2014; Jeary and Mwitwa, 2022; Teschemacher et al., 2024; Serenje et al., 2025). While there is a common view that land is abundant (Manda and Banda, 2023), there are potential tensions between sectoral policies. For example, there are important questions over how to achieve the stated priorities of increasing agricultural production while stemming the loss of forest cover, which may incur trade-offs. Supporting sustainable rural livelihoods while reducing the impact of cooking fuel production requires co-ordination between the energy, agriculture and forestry actors. It is therefore vital to further develop an integrated approach to policy across sectors, understanding synergies and trade-offs between policy objectives, to enhance social and environmental outcomes.

In Zambia, several studies have examined past land-use and land cover. The national Integrated Land-Use Assessments (GRZ, 2009, 2016) observed Zambia's forest cover shrinking from approximately 49.9 Mha to 45.9 Mha between 2008 and 2014. National survey studies have linked forest degradation and loss to charcoal production (GRZ, 2017), and agricultural expansion (Ngoma et al., 2021). Spatially explicit analyses have contributed understand of the relationship between forest loss and the expansion of farmland (Drigo, 2016; Phiri et al., 2019, 2023) and

expansion of settlements (Phiri et al., 2019). Phiri et al. (2019) also reported forest recovery, but at much lower rates than deforestation. Household surveys and focus groups have been used to further investigate the influence of factors including: socio-economics (Handavu et al., 2019), governance of charcoal supply chains (Kaywala, 2020), cooking fuels demand and supply dynamics (Tembo et al., 2015).

Fewer studies have explored future scenarios of land cover change (LCC) and potential interventions to address it. Vinya et al. (2011) examined historic data then projected trends to 2030, suggesting an increase in the rate of deforestation, and suggested several measures which could halt forest cover loss including enhancing soil quality and erosion control, afforestation, woodland regeneration and agroforestry. Richardson et al. (2021) utilised systems dynamics, their results indicating that agricultural intensification alone would not slow down deforestation, as population growth drives further expansion of urban areas and demand for charcoal. Utilising neural network analysis, Chisanga et al. (2024) projected LCC to 2030 noting further expansion of urban areas at the expense of forest loss, but a slight reduction in agricultural area as compared to 2020.

A tool to support decision-making

Modelling approaches can be used to estimate future land cover but also – importantly – to support stakeholders to envision alternative approaches to future land-use (Verburg et al., 2019). Methods including statistical, econometric, spatial, optimisation and integrated approaches each have strengths and limitations (Noszczyk, 2019). Among those which create projections of future LUC, the choice of modelling paradigm can lead to substantially different projections (Brown et al., 2021). It is therefore vital to select or develop tools based on careful consideration of the research objectives and data availability (Noszczyk, 2019; Hewitt et al., 2022).

While the Zambia-focused studies outlined above provide a good basis for understanding past land-use dynamics and some projections of how land transitions may evolve into the future, they require specialist data, tools and expertise, and most snapshots of the past or already simulated projections into the future. This limits their utilisation by a wider range of policy-makers and land-use planners to explore alternative narratives of change. There is a need for accessible tools which facilitate the examination of potential implications, synergies and trade-offs between the land aspects of national development plans by policy-makers, land-planners and other stakeholders. Critically, these tools should use publicly available data which are updated regularly and are open to public scrutiny, to increase the transparency of analyses.

To address those gaps, this study co-developed a conceptual model of land-use change dynamics, and a method to quantify the land cover change for future scenarios - a new open-access Excel-based tool "*LandFutures_Zambia*" (Cronin et al., 2025). This paper presents both, along with illustrative results, with the aim of bringing together the multiple conversations that affect land, which often happen in policy silos. Together, these elements aim to facilitate dialogue between decision-makers with diverse sectoral knowledge and objectives, to assist them in developing a shared understanding of how their goals and actions both rely on and impact land, and how they interact with synergies, trade-offs and uncertainties.

Ideas for further applications of the tools are described. Importantly, the tool can provide a basis for assessing land-based greenhouse gas emissions pathways and mitigation options. This study

illustrates how the conceptual model and scenario analysis can enhance understanding of climate change adaptation and resilience alongside mitigation.

2 Method

A first step was to develop an understanding of the key dynamics of land-use and land cover change in Zambia through a wide literature review. Simultaneously, narratives of future socio-economic development and land-use change in Zambia were developed. Building work conducted under the *Greening the Recovery in Zambia and Ghana* project (Nyambe-Mubanga et al., 2023) and the *Climate Compatible Growth* programme (Broad et al., 2024), which developed alternative scenarios for Zambia's development using a participatory method. For this study, the elements of those scenarios that affect or rely on land were further considered; (as described in the supplementary information (SI.1)).

Drawing on both activities, an initial conceptual map of land-use change dynamics was constructed, depicting how various drivers and processes could lead to land cover transitions, such as from forest to cropland or from grassland to settlements. Based on the literature and historic data, the main 'processes' by which land cover change predominantly occurs were identified as: expansion of settlements, expansion of cropland, clearance of trees for charcoal production, and the regeneration of degraded cropland and deforested areas. These dynamic processes were represented in a quantitative Excel tool, *LandFutures_Zambia*. Based on user-defined drivers, the tool estimates the areas of land that are affected by each process and then calculates the land cover conversions that take place when each process occurs, in order to derive a timeseries of future land cover change for different scenarios.

In the tool, the land cover classification scheme is based on six classifications (settlements, cropland, grassland, forest, wetland, other land), selected for consistency with the Zambia Integrated Land Use Assessment report (GRZ, 2016) and Phiri et al. (2023), from which key data were extracted for the quantitative analysis. Other data were drawn from sources including the ZamStats, World Bank and FAO databases. Importantly, assumptions representing the land cover conversions that occur when the processes happen are derived from the historic land cover matrix presented by Phiri et al. (2023).

To validate the modelling approach, a stakeholder workshop was held in Lusaka in November 2024. Participants included representatives from Government (1), civil society (1) and researchers from universities (3) and independent organisations (5) with diverse expertise, including on farming practices, infrastructure development, land tenure and mining. Through discussions of the model structure and key assumptions, the validity of the approach was confirmed, including the representation of the most important dynamics and uncertainties. Understanding of key elements were enriched, such as the various processes driving settlement expansion and the relationship between farming and charcoal production. The conceptual model and Excel tool were then revised, incorporating core recommendations from the stakeholders.

3 Results

3.1 Conceptual model

Figure 1 shows the conceptual model of land-use change in Zambia. Drivers of land-use change including socio-economic trends and specific policy interventions (green boxes) lead to various

intermediate implications (pink nodes), which determine changes to land cover types such as settlements, cropland, forest etc (purple nodes). Changes to the drivers ultimately lead to conversion between the land cover types. The interconnections illustrate how several processes can be affected by multiple alternative kinds of intervention.

As illustrated in Figure 1, **Error! Reference source not found.** land-use change in Zambia is influenced by a combination of economic, social, and environmental factors. Rapidly growing population is driving increasing demands for settlements, agricultural products and cooking fuels. These and other important dynamics are outlined below.

Agricultural land (cropland) expansion is mainly driven by increasing demands for food required by Zambia's growing population, which is expected to reach approximately 40 million people by 2050, relative to 21.9 million today (World Bank, n.d.). Additional demands for crops are expected to arise from the setting of biofuel blending targets and policies driving an increase in production of cash crops for export (GRZ, 2022a). While maize is not recommended for biofuels due to its critical importance for food, key feedstock options include sugarcane or cassava for bioethanol and sunflower or soybean for biodiesel, which might lend themselves to cultivation by different kinds of farming (e.g. large-scale vs smallholders via outgrower schemes) (FAO and GRZ, 2020).

Requirement for agricultural land to meet current and new demands is determined by the intensity of production of key crops (i.e. yields). For many smallholder farmers, yields are limited by their access to inputs such as fertilizers, pesticides and machinery due to the high costs, but also by a lack of information about their most appropriate use (Teschemacher et al., 2024). Average yields for most crops in Zambia are therefore substantially lower than the theoretical potential (GRZ, 2022b). Increasing yields could potentially reduce the need to expand areas under cultivation.

Several ways to increase crop yields are being pursued, which have various advantages and challenges. A significant portion of the national budget is spent on supporting farmers to afford and access inputs such as fertilizers and climate resilient seed varieties, through the Comprehensive Agriculture Support Program, formerly known as Farmer Input Support programme (GRZ, 2024). The newly introduced Sustainable Agriculture Financing Facility addresses limited access to finance by smallholder and emergent farmers with potential to increase crop yield on existing cropland by venturing into mechanised and irrigation farming practices. The Farm Block Development Programme promotes commercial farming and supports smallholders to adopt modern farming techniques through training and extension services provided within the programme (GRZ, 2023b). Further efforts to increase private sector involvement include the provision of technical advisory services and catalytic investment for agribusinesses by NGOs (e.g. Musika and Prospero).

Simultaneously, government programmes and development funders (e.g. World Bank, 2019) are increasingly focused on improving the longer-term resilience of farming production and livelihoods by encouraging the adoption of climate-smart agriculture techniques (CSA), possibly reducing the rate of cropland expansion (Ngoma et al., 2021). These include conservation agriculture (minimum soil disturbance, crop rotations, permanent soil cover), improved water management, sustainable irrigation and agroforestry (CIAT and World Bank, 2017), which place the focus on increasing resilience to climate change impacts and reducing soil degradation. Key challenges to CSA are the high labour requirements for manual weeding which may have undesired gender workload distribution dynamics, where labour input such ploughing (which is

Figure 1 Conceptual model of land cover change illustrating the connections between different drivers (green boxes) and key land cover types (purple nodes). The different implications of changes in drivers are illustrated by pink nodes, showing the processes induced by changes in drivers affecting different land cover types.

traditionally a male activity) is significantly reduced, while ripping and land preparation increasingly become a typical female work activity. As climate-smart agriculture practices are deployed, farmers may experience a decline in yields before the benefits of the organic soil improvements are achieved, which often leads farmers to revert to traditional techniques with chemical fertilizers and tilling.

Another key driver of cropland expansion in Zambia is land degradation (Mweshi et al., 2022; Neina et al., 2022). Drivers include nutrient depletion due to mono-cropping with low use of fertilisers, rising soil acidity, degradation of soil structure due to tilling, and challenges with water management. When soils lose fertility, it is common for farmers to open new fields by clearing trees to take advantage of the fertile soils beneath. This further exacerbates nutrient depletion locally, as leaves no longer fall and enrich the soils with organic matter, and increases water erosion (Neina et al., 2022).

Settlement expansion is occurring by three main mechanisms. First, job and livelihood prospects lead people to move from rural to urban areas. Second, there is a trend of more affluent people moving from city centres outwards to suburbs of lower density i.e. expansion of lower density peri-urban areas. Third, there is urban to rural migration - new settlements are being purposely initiated by government to uplift rural living standards, increase agricultural productivity and improve critical infrastructure, e.g. roads, health facilities, schools (GRZ, 2018a).

Internal migration drives changes in settlements, while it both drives and is driven by changes to cropland. For instance, large-scale loss of soil productivity and land degradation, reduced rainfall and unpredictable rainfall patterns in the South of Zambia have driven people to abandon croplands and migrate northwards, bringing with them different agricultural practices, in particular more clear cutting (Zhunusova et al., 2025). **New mining projects** also drive migrations, adding to abandonment of settlements and cropland in some areas, and to new land conversion to cropland, settlements and commercial industries in the vicinity of the new mining sites, to meet the demands from the mining community (Tiamgne et al., 2021).

Cooking fuels. Natural forest cover is reduced by the clearance of trees to make space but also the **removal of the wood** for its own sake. In Zambia, firewood and charcoal are the primary cooking fuels for 56.8% and 26.9% of households respectively (ZamStats, 2024). In rural areas, the main source of energy is firewood. This is usually collected as dead wood; as such, “the impact of firewood harvesting on forest degradation is considered to be negligible” (GRZ, 2016; Richardson et al., 2021). In contrast, production of charcoal, which is the dominant cooking fuel for urban households, typically involves felling of hardwood trees (Richardson et al., 2021). In theory, wood supply could meet charcoal demand sustainably (Drigo, 2016). However, particularly in hotspots around the main urban areas, wood harvesting for charcoal exceeds natural regeneration (GRZ, 2017; Moombe et al., 2020; Richardson et al., 2021). Some land cleared for charcoal is used for agriculture, leading many to state that agricultural expansion is the main driver of deforestation. However, analysis of satellite data indicated that only approximately 25% becomes cropland within 7 years (Sedano et al., 2022). In areas that have been cleared, fire risk is so significantly increased that regeneration to forest cover with mature trees is unlikely.

As well as efforts to reduce charcoal demands and make production more efficient with improved kilns, many **interventions aiming to reduce forest degradation and deforestation** focus on forest management and livelihoods, e.g. Community Forest Management programs (GRZ, 2018b) and the Integrated Forest Landscape Program (GRZ ZIFLP, n.d.). Efforts to actively **restore areas**

of degraded forest include the regeneration project in Muchinga and Eastern province, focusing on building resilience to climate impacts through ecosystem restoration and sustainable land use (GRZ, 2019). Land-use activities are variously regulated and enforced in **designated areas** including Zambia's National Parks, Game Management Areas, Forest Reserves.

Going forward, LCC trends may be accentuated by Zambian growth plans. Agriculture, mining, manufacturing and tourism have been identified as main drivers of economic transformation agenda (GRZ, 2022a). The resilience of agriculture to climate change impacts, opportunities for growth and value addition all depend on effective environmental management, while tourism depends on Zambia's rich ecosystems and natural environments. Integrated understanding of land-use change is therefore needed to form the base of any decision-making affecting land futures in Zambia. This conceptual model could provide a useful mapping tool to support this process.

3.2 LandFutures_Zambia tool description

Tool structure

To enhance the exploration of future land-use scenarios, a subset of the dynamics shown in Figure 1 (See SI.2) has been implemented in a quantitative tool using a simulation approach. Considering the transitions that are most dominant in the historical data, and which were identified by the stakeholders, five 'land-use change processes' are represented in the tool: the expansion of settlements, expansion of agricultural land, forest clearance due to charcoal production, natural and assisted regeneration of abandoned cropland, and conversion of other land types. Note, internal migration and the protection of designated areas are not represented as the dynamics for these less clear, especially with respect to the visibility of their effect in national statistics. For example, restrictions on land clearance for charcoal or agriculture in specific areas can drive their displacement to other regions.

To enable its use by various stakeholders, the tool is implemented in Excel, with all formulae and input data transparent and open access. It is available for application and further development by other researchers and stakeholders. As illustrated in Figure 2, the tool has a modular structure; data are separated into different worksheets to enable further development in one or several modules without breaking the overall framework.

The rate of each land-use change 'process' is determined by one or more 'drivers'. These are set by the user on a single worksheet, which contains a pre-defined Reference scenario and fields in which the user can enter assumptions for key parameters for two additional scenarios, such as crop yields, biofuel blending targets, demands for charcoal, the rate of urbanisation, cropland abandonment and regeneration. Values are specified for the 2030 and 2050 and the model interpolates yearly values in between. From those, the tool simulates the future settlement expansion, cropland expansion, forest clearance for charcoal, and land regeneration. It then combines these projections to calculate a matrix of land cover change based on assumptions about the specific land cover transitions that take place when each process occurs, which are derived from historic data (Phiri et al., 2023).

Key results are displayed on a single sheet, which shows for each scenario, the overall land cover changes, average annual land cover change figures for the time periods 2018-2030 and 2031-2050, and a set of other results of interest, including crop demands, charcoal demands, the area

cleared for charcoal production and the areas of degraded land which are regenerated into cultivated cropland or natural ecosystems.

Figure 2. Modular structure of the LandFutures_Zambia tool showing structure of data inputs (both default data and user input), calculation sheets and type of results currently displayed by the tool.

Computational procedure

The logic of the calculations is illustrated in Figure 3, showing the drivers, intermediate variables and key assumptions for the five processes represented in the tool. Each process is described below, while further details of the calculations are given in the SI.3.

Figure 3. Schematic of the land-use change processes modelled in the tool

The expansion of urban settlements is projected based on population growth and the urbanisation rate, which together set the future urban population, and the urban population density, which can be changed to represent different types of population shifts.

Crop demands are projected based on population growth, per capita demands (assumed to be constant), and requirements for biofuel blending. The area required to meet those demands is then determined by the future crop yields. The user can set the future yields for 12 individual crops (maize, cassava and sugarcane) or aggregated crop groups (other grains, pulses, fruit and vegetables etc), in order to explore the impact of interventions in different kinds of farming, or climate impacts. Cropland expansion is determined by two further factors: i) the rate at which cropland is abandoned and ii) the proportion of additional cropland expansion which occurs in previously “under-utilised” land (See explanation in SI.3). The user can set these latter factors to represent respectively: the prevention of cropland abandonment (e.g. through improved soil and water management, agroforestry etc), and the regeneration of degraded soils or increased access to inputs that facilitates farmers to cultivate more of the land that is available to them. It is currently assumed that crop production is the dominant driver of agricultural land expansion, with small levels of livestock mainly supported on mixed-use agricultural land,

To project deforestation by charcoal production, the tool estimates future charcoal demand based on the user-defined usage of traditional and improved efficiency charcoal cookstoves in

urban and rural areas. It is assumed that only charcoal produced from natural forests causes deforestation, so wood demand from natural forests is calculated based on user-defined levels of sustainable forest management and use of efficient kilns. The area cleared is calculated based on the fraction of non-renewable biomass and the average biomass density of forests. Finally, a portion is subtracted representing the area that is later used for agriculture, assuming (25% of the land cleared for charcoal later becomes cropland, with the rest unlikely to regenerate (A2C, 2021; Sedano et al., 2022)). The user can therefore explore the impact of increased sustainable forest management efficient kilns or more co-ordinated planning of charcoal production alongside agricultural activities. The areas of land undergoing other land cover conversions are set by the user directly as hectares per year, rather than via drivers. Increasing the rate of conversion from cropland to either grassland or forest can represent assisted regeneration of abandoned areas back to natural habitats. Higher rates of other conversion can represent afforestation reforestation or wetland regeneration.

Uses of the model

LandFutures_Zambia can be used to address policy questions of various levels of detail.

First, by examining the reference scenario and changing just one or two drivers, the model can be used to estimate land cover change for specific assumptions. For example:

- i. How much settlement expansion might occur, given future population growth and different urbanisation levels?
- ii. How much cropland expansion might we expect, given future population growth and crop yield assumptions?
- iii. How much extra land cover change would be driven by biofuel blending targets and crop choices?

Second, it can be used to examine the relative importance or combined effects of multiple trends or interventions. For example:

- iv. Which drivers have a bigger impact on land cover change?
- v. How much of the expected cropland expansion could be mitigated with interventions targeting yield improvements, cropland abandonment or the use of under-utilized land?
- vi. How much could sustainable forest management, efficient kilns or alternative cooking technologies reduce forest clearance due to charcoal?

Third, it can be used to explore land cover implications of more holistic scenarios. These could depict alternative approaches to planning such as prioritisation of nature vs production, or socio-economic development pathways driven by, for example, more “centralised” vs “decentralised” approaches to governance and infrastructure.

In these ways, the tool can help facilitate conversations on land-use change by contributing quantified estimates of land cover impacts alongside broader questions around the social, environmental and technical aspects of development. The substantial thinking that is needed outside the tool to decide sensible values for the model drivers to contextualise the results is as important as the numbers. For example, important questions to consider include: how can yield improvements be achieved considering the challenges faced by smallholder farmers and the role of commercial actors; how might changes to charcoal production affect people in the supply chain; and what are the social and biodiversity implications of alternative interventions aiming to restore degraded soils or increase reforestation?

3.3 Illustrative results from LandFutures_Zambia

To depict the continuation of historic land transition trends akin to a “business as usual” case, a Reference scenario is defined with user inputs shown in the SI.4. This leads to the estimate of future land cover change shown in Figure 4, against which other future scenarios can be compared.

Figure 4 Land cover change in the Reference scenario defined with user inputs shown in the SI.4

In 2018, Zambia was estimated to have 44.1 Mha of forest land, representing 59% of its land cover (Phiri et al., 2023). The reference scenario indicates that if current trends continue, up to 6.3 Mha of forest could be lost by 2050, at an average pace of 198,000 ha forest lost per year. Expansion of settlements accounts for only 3-4% of this forest loss. The majority is caused by land clearance for cropland, which accounts for 79% in 2018 but is projected to fall to 60% in 2050, because the role of charcoal production increases in importance, rising from 18% in 2018 to 37% by 2050, driven by urbanisation as well as the growing population.

While the majority of cropland serves to produce food for Zambia’s population, producing feedstocks for biofuels could drive further land cover change. Specifically, producing crop feedstocks to achieve E10 and B5 biofuel blending targets by 2050 would require an additional 9,100 ha/yr of cropland, leading the total cropland area to be 2.3% higher than in the Reference scenario in 2050. Due to their yields and conversion factors, producing these levels of bioethanol and biodiesel would require less land if sugarcane and sunflower crops were prioritised as feedstocks rather than cassava and soybean. Increasing production of crops for export or increasing per capita demands for agricultural products would further increase the land required for agriculture.

Some of the need to expand cropland could be mitigated by increasing yields. For example, increasing average crop yields by 10% by 2030 and 50% by 2050 could reduce the average annual forest loss by 32,000 ha/yr relative to the Reference scenario. Historic data show the average yields of most crops in Zambia (with the exception of cassava) have not substantially increased since 2000 (FAOSTAT, n.d.). These levels of yield improvement would therefore be a radical achievement.

Much of the projected cropland expansion is due to assumptions about cropland abandonment; comparison of historic data indicated as much as 88,000 ha/yr could be abandoned each year (see more detail in the SI.3), highlighting that interventions targeted to reduce this could be a major potential lever for reducing cropland expansion.

Also important is the extent to which cropland expansion can use previously 'underutilised land', which is identified as approximately 5 Mha in the historic data by the discrepancy between available cropland and cultivated area (See SI.3). While part of this may be due to the use of land for rotational cropping systems which leave areas fallow for some years, it indicates a significant portion of potentially available cropland is not fully cultivated due to farmers' limited access to inputs and soil degradation. It therefore provides a quantified estimate of the area that could potentially be brought into cultivation by interventions targeting these factors. Together, these factors emphasise the need to continue enhancing the focus on climate smart, conservation agriculture techniques that prioritise soil health, as well as active restoration of degraded soils. Addressing these could reduce the necessity to expand cropland into forested or grassland areas.

In the Reference scenario, charcoal production causes an increasing level of deforestation each year due to the rapidly growing population and urbanisation; charcoal forest loss grows from approximately 31,000 ha/yr in 2018 to 95,000 ha/yr in 2050. This could be mitigated by demand or supply-side approaches. For example, to keep the yearly forest clearance due to charcoal steady close to 2018 levels, the percentage of urban households using charcoal (with traditional cookstoves) as their primary fuel would need to reduce from 60% to approximately 20% by 2050. Increasing the use of efficient kilns so they produced 100% of charcoal by 2050 would reduce the annual forest loss from charcoal by 33% compared to the Reference scenario.

Considering future land transitions, the relative importance of these demand-side, supply-side and land-management related drivers depends on the changes that stakeholders believe could be achievable (and desirable). To explore the combined impact of the various drivers of land-use change, two scenarios are illustrated, depicting examples of best and worst cases for land cover change.

- i. In the first scenario, "High land cover change" (HCC), demands for crops and charcoal are assumed high as ambitious targets are set for biofuel blending, and uptake of clean cooking options is slow. It also assumes that crop yield improvement measures fail, while increasing droughts and less predictable rainy seasons cause an average yield reduction by 10% by 2030 and 30% by 2050. The majority of smallholder and commercial farmers are assumed to continue with high input farming practices which, combined with climate change impacts and other deforestation, leads to an acceleration of soil degradation and cropland abandonment. Lack of funding, training and conservation support leads to low rates of cropland and forest regeneration.
- ii. In the second scenario, "Low land cover change" (LCC), demands for agricultural products are assumed low, as no increase in biofuel production or trade is expected. Substantial yield improvements are assumed for all crops due to increased up-take of low input, climate smart agricultural techniques which achieve both gradual improvements and resilience to droughts and floods. Conservation agriculture, agroforestry and farmer training and support lead to a major decrease in soil degradation and there is also substantial effort to restore degraded soils. Reforestation to restore areas of damaged or cleared forests further supports efforts to restore nearby cropland and the achievement of sustainable farming practices.

Depicting these two alternative futures in LandFutures_Zambia (see input driver values in SI.4) leads to significantly different land cover change trajectories compared to the Reference scenario, see Figure 5. Implementing the measures envisioned in the Low land cover change scenario could lead to 1.4 Mha reduction in the total cropland required to meet future demands by 2050 as compared to the Reference, and 4.1 Mha as compared to the High land cover change scenario. By 2050, wood demands from natural forest are 2.3 times greater in the High LCC than in Low LCC scenario.

Figure 5. Land cover changes in three scenarios: Reference (continuation of historical trends), Low Land Cover change (assuming high yields, lower demand, land management to increase resilience to climate change), and High Land Cover Change (assuming failure of efficiency improvement measures, high demands, and high climate change impacts).

Across the three scenarios, the expansion in the cropland area and increased charcoal production comes at the expense of forest loss; as expected this is higher in the HCC scenario than the LCC scenarios. Some is mitigated by regeneration of degraded croplands and assisted reforestation. Over the 2018-2050 period, these lead to a total net forest loss of 9.8 Mha in the High Land Cover Change scenario, versus 4.4 Mha in the Low Land Cover Change scenario.

4 Discussion

This study highlights several questions regarding how some of the land-use change drivers and processes work in reality, which point to important areas of uncertainty and policy questions.

Yield improvements. While *LandFutures_Zambia* estimates the impact of yield improvements on the land required to meet crop demands, it is well noted that yields depend on various economic and environmental factors. As shown in Figure 1, different approaches might be pursued to improve yields. For smallholder farmers, these include increasing access to farming inputs or increased conservation agriculture techniques, each with different implications for input costs and farming revenues, long-term soil health and climate change resilience. Increasing the role of commercial farmers could raise average yields but may destabilise smallholder livelihoods and be linked to large-scale land acquisitions (Matenga and Hichaambwa, 2017; IPES-Food, 2024). When considering yield changes, it is crucial to consider gradual changes but also the increasing frequency of extreme events, such as the major drought that caused a major part of Zambia's maize crop to fail in 2024.

Thus, the study prompts stakeholders to consider in detail: what yield improvements are realistically achievable, by which farmers and crops, with which approaches, and how alternative approaches align with different environmental and social trends or outcomes?

Cropland degradation and use of underutilized land. Substantial investigation and generation of evidence is required to improve understanding of other drivers of cropland expansion, namely cropland degradation, cropland abandonment and under-utilised land, and how they can be addressed. The literature review and stakeholder engagement indicated that efforts to develop

common understanding of the definitions, causes and mitigation possibilities for these issues would be valuable.

Livelihoods as drivers of land-use change. Across several of the land-use dynamics identified, the study highlighted the importance of livelihoods as drivers. By simulating the land cover conversions that would need to occur to meet the various crop and fuel demands, *LandFutures_Zambia* assumes ‘supply’ always neatly meets demand and so stops short of representing additional factors which might affect the decision-making of land managers. Specifically, it assumes that if yields increase, cropland expansion is reduced and if charcoal demands reduce, tree harvesting is reduced. While it is likely appropriate at national level to assume the supply for land-based products balance demands, it probably overlooks local or short-term dynamics. The conceptual model notes the vital importance of agriculture and charcoal production for livelihoods, especially in rural areas.

Regarding agriculture, several studies raise that in fact yield increases can lead farmers to use the increased income to expand their cropland (Adolph et al., 2022; Richardson et al., 2021). As many smallholder farmers cultivate less land than available due to limited inputs or labour (Adu-Baffour et al., 2019), it might be expected that increased income would enable them, in particular, to expand the area they cultivate. Ngoma et al. (2021) found no evidence that adopting climate-smart agriculture affects cropland expansion, concluding that “relying only on climate-smart agriculture as a means to spare forests may be risky.”

To reduce forest loss, yield improvement efforts would therefore need to be combined with incentives or restrictions on cropland expansion, thereby preventing further forest conversion potentially driven by the reduced land-use costs associated with higher crop yields. This points to a trade-off between the policy goals of increasing production – for the sake of improving food security and economic value – and reducing deforestation.

Along with agriculture, the vital importance of charcoal production as an income generator for rural communities is widely understood (Branch et al., 2022). In Zambia, people turn to additional charcoal production when agricultural income is less reliable e.g. in times of drought (Gonzalez, 2020). Further, charcoal bans are likely to be difficult to implement and disproportionately punitive (Branch et al., 2022). The study therefore highlights the need for policies which support alternative reliable livelihood alternatives, alongside any charcoal restrictions or demand-side measures.

Interactions between charcoal production and farming. To develop the Excel tool, it was necessary to parameterise the relationship between charcoal production and agriculture as drivers of land cover change. The model assumes says 20% of land cleared for charcoal later becomes cropland (See SI.3). It is likely this dynamic differs between districts and in time. While this is an uncertainty in the model, it highlights the need to better understand and collect data on these dynamics in charcoal hotspot areas and beyond. While it might be thought desirable to prevent encroachment of agriculture following charcoal production, considering the full picture of LCC drivers suggests it might be worth considering the potential value of co-ordinated charcoal and agricultural expansion, which could be consistent with more formalisation of both sectors.

Ideas for further applications

The conceptual model and Excel tool have been built for Zambia. Specific land-use and land cover change dynamics differ between regions, however the *types* of dynamics are likely to bear

similarities. Deforestation and agricultural expansion are common trends in many areas in the Global South, though at different rates, driven by different ecological and economic, political factors (Winkler et al., 2021). To adapt the conceptual model and Excel tool for **another national context**, a researcher would need to: i) conduct a literature review and stakeholder engagement to inform the conceptual model; ii) obtain and examine national level historic land cover change data; iii) confirm or adjust the representation of the key land cover change processes in the LandFutures tool; iv) develop scenarios of future land-use change, including narratives and quantification of future land cover.

The Excel tool is structured as transparently as possible to allow further development and application. To facilitate exploration of additional elements of the conceptual model and issues described above, the following are suggested as key areas for development:

First, **different types of farming** could be considered in the tool with the addition of farming 'archetypes' for which typical yields, crop or livestock choices, and GHG factors are defined. Scenario drivers could be introduced to set the areas covered by different farming types, which would allow exploration of the impacts of policies to incentivise or facilitate various agricultural transition, for example increased role of large-scale commercial farming, or higher input smallholder farming vs. conservation agriculture. Additional representation of farming archetypes would allow exploration of land-use implications of, for example, increasing levels of total livestock or herd sizes.

Second, **disaggregation of the different types of 'under-utilised land'** would allow deeper exploration within the model of the value of different types of policy intervention, e.g. efforts to restore degraded soils, increase farmers' access to inputs, or increase/decrease the practice of rotational cropping.

Third, representing **dynamics related to internal migration**. This would also involve adding detail on the processes which lead to changes in settlement land by disaggregating settlements into areas with different population densities and modelling their changes separately, and by introducing settlement abandonment as well as expansion. Furthermore, developers could explore methods to represent the links between industrial development, changes to settlements and changes to agricultural land (expansion and abandonment), e.g. to quantify how the opening of new mines, combined with drought-driven cropland abandonment could drive the movement of settlements and cropland.

Greater spatial detail would allow a more detailed representation of the land cover change that occurs when each process happens. While the tool currently assumes a single value for these dynamics at national level, in reality the land cover transitions will differ between regions, depending on the existing land cover, and they will change with time as land cover changes. For example, in a heavily forested area, if a settlement expands, it is likely that the required area is cleared of forest, whereas if the forest is already depleted, it is likely that a greater part of the new settlement land will be converted from grassland or cropland. Whilst these insights might be useful for local decision making, a greater spatial detail will add further complexity to the tool, potentially making it inaccessible to some users.

A key application of this tool would be to facilitate **greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions analysis**. Inclusion of GHG emission factors, which indicate the quantity of GHG (in tCO₂eq) that are emitted or sequestered by each parcel of land when undergoing land-use or land cover change, or remaining unchanged, would facilitate projections of future land-based emissions, along with

analysis of mitigation options. This could, in particular, aid the development of climate mitigation targets and strategies for Nationally Determined Contributions.

Finally, the tool could be used to calculate the **potential for improved biomass fuels**, such as pellets and briquettes from crop and forestry residues for cooking or larger scale application such as electricity and heat generation. A key uncertainty and challenge for the development of these supply chains relates to the logistics of aggregating feedstocks from many smallholder farmers, so this would benefit from greater representation of the various farming archetypes described above. Linking the estimates of improved biomass fuels could allow users to deepen understanding of how changes in the agriculture and forest sectors could have synergies with clean cooking strategies.

5 Conclusions

This study drew on the expertise of diverse literature and expert stakeholders to co-create tools to support decision making on land-use transitions in Zambia. Whilst the conceptual model gives insights into the key land processes and identifies direct and indirect drivers of land change, the quantitative tool, *LandFutures_Zambia*, estimates land cover transitions for different future socio-economic narratives. This allows exploration of the individual or combined effects of some trends or measures, e.g. forest management, kiln efficiency and clean cooking measures in curbing deforestation. Finally, the tools facilitate the exploration of more holistic socio-economic development scenarios, in order to enhance policy coherence, e.g. exploration of integrated agriculture – forestry planning, balancing priorities between nature conservation and production.

The study highlights need for further study to understand the definitions, causes and mitigation possibilities for cropland degradation, abandonment and under-utilised land, to inform a more efficient use of land and reduce the rate of deforestation whilst meeting increasing demands for food, fuels, and settlements. Further research is also needed to better characterise the links between different types of farms, farm management, internal migration, charcoal production and consumption and forest loss.

The Excel tool is fully accessible, with transparent assumptions and calculations, using publicly available data. It is formatted and presented such that users can create scenarios based on a set of drivers, test sensitivities, scrutinise assumptions and further develop the tool for ongoing research.

6 Data Availability

The Excel tool *LandFutures_Zambia* is available for download at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15091171>

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Supplementary Information

SI.1 – Narratives

The conceptual model of land-use change presented in this paper was developed in part through the examination of socio-economic development narratives. Full details of the cross-sector narratives are provided in Nyambe-Mubanga et al. (2023) and Broad et al. (2024). Below are versions of the land-related aspects of those scenarios, which were used in the development in this study.

The *Centralised* scenario is driven by a preference for policy approaches that prioritise ‘an export-led trade strategy’, and investment in large-scale infrastructure, leveraging ‘public-private partnership (PPP) investment’. There is high migration from rural to urban areas, and thus an expansion of towns and cities. In the agriculture sector, there is a drive to increase production for export. Foreign investment is attracted into the sector, and there is a shift towards larger-scale higher input, demand-led agriculture. Irrigation is provided by large-scale infrastructure, possibly associated with large hydropower dams/reservoirs. There is a significant increase in production of ethanol from sugarcane and cassava, and the refineries also produce some biogas. It is noted that sugarcane is likely to require irrigation. There is less small-scale bioenergy. The large-scale approach to energy infrastructure and increased urban migration lead to lower use of woodfuel and charcoal in rural and also urban areas reducing this driver of deforestation.

The *Decentralised* scenario has a preference for policy approaches that reflect the President’s stated interest in “decentralisation and devolution of various central government functions... that will be better managed at the local level with appreciation for local challenges”¹. There is a focus on supporting sustainable rural livelihoods, which leads to urban migration trailing off and not much urban expansion. To facilitate this, location specific extension services, including education on climate smart agricultural practices are increased and strengthened. This leads to greater use of drought tolerant crops, better water efficiency, drop irrigation and the stimulation of locally appropriate markets. Furthermore, there is an increase in commodity development associations, which helps communities to add value to their agricultural products and retain it locally. Regarding bioenergy, the focus is on local production and use for example, for household/farm biogas, and on sustainable woodfuel and charcoal production. Governance of forests by traditional leaders is supported and strengthened, along with management by community associations. In line with this, there is a different trend around land tenure as the state stops acquiring land and converting to leasehold.

¹ Presidential speech to National Assembly, 10th September 2021, p.44

SI.2 - Representation of conceptual model in LandFutures_Zambia

Figure SI.2 shows the dynamics of the conceptual model which are represented in the LandFutures_Zambia tool.

Figure SI.2 Drivers and process from the conceptual model that are represented in the LandFutures_Zambia model (coloured boxes) and currently not represented in the tool (grey boxes).

SI.3 - LandFutures_Zambia – additional detail

Additional details are provided on the computational procedure of the LandFutures_Zambia tool.

Expansion of settlements

The tool projects the future urban population based on the population growth and the urbanisation rate. The total population growth rate is assumed to be the same across all scenarios, while the user sets the rate of urbanisation for the scenarios by specifying the rate of urban population growth for 2030 and 2050. It is assumed that the average urban population density continues to rise as seen in historic data, which is consistent with a continued trend of people moving from rural to urban areas. The total settlement area for each year is calculated by the formula:

$$\text{Settlement area [ha]} = \text{Urban population [ha]} \div \text{Urban population density [ha]}$$

Expansion of agricultural land

The tool projects future demands for crops in two categories: food/fiber/fodder, energy crops. The demand for each category is calculated separately, then they are summed to give total crop demand in t/yr for each year until 2050. Demands for food/fibre/fodder are projected based on population growth, and per capita demands (which are assumed to remain constant). Demands for energy crops are projected based on blending targets for bioethanol and biodiesel and the choice of the dominant feedstock crop for each. The user can choose the main crop feedstock

for each fuel: bioethanol can be made from sugarcane or cassava, while biodiesel can be made from soybeans or sunflower.

To make the model inputs manageable, crops are aggregated into a set of groups based on analysis of historic data of cropping areas, production statistics and yields (FAO; ZamStats) and their interest for the Zambian scenarios. Maize, cassava and sugarcane are each represented singly due to their importance as food and biofuel crops, and their yield characteristics (sugarcane is substantially higher than any other and unlikely to rise in the future, while maize and cassava are the focus of yield improvement efforts). Other crops are represented as aggregated groups: other cereals, fruit and vegetables, nuts, oilseeds, pulses, roots and tubers, other food, and non-food crops. The user has the option to set the future yields in [t/ha] for each crop or crop group in 2030 and 2050. These represent the average yields across the country.

The cropland area required to meet future demands is then calculated for each crop group and summed using the formula:

$$\text{Area required [ha]} = \sum_i^n \text{Future demand}_i [\text{t}] / \text{Yield}_i \left[\frac{\text{t}}{\text{ha}} \right]$$

where i indicates the crop groups, and n is the total number of crop groups.

Besides yields, the amount of cropland *expansion* depends on two additional factors: (1) the rate at which cropland is abandoned, and (2) the amount of cropland expansion which occurs in ‘under-utilised land’.

On the first, no published estimates of the rate of cropland abandonment were available, so a historic rate of cropland abandonment was estimated. Analysis of historical trends showed that increased demands driven by the growing population would account for only approximately one third of the observed cropland expansion, indicating that the rest would be due to cropland abandonment.

On the second, the concept of ‘underutilized land’ is derived from the fact that substantially more land is identified as cropland in satellite data than in production statistics. While satellite data analyses identify approximately 8 Mha as cropland in 2018 (GRZ, 2016; Phiri et al., 2023), production survey data indicate approximately 2.8 Mha are cultivated in recent years (ZAMSTATS; FAO). This can be explained by a combination of factors: cultivation of available land being limited by farmers’ access to inputs, the use of shifting agricultural systems which leaves some areas fallow for various periods, and soil degradation. We assume that the difference between the two statistics represents ‘under-utilised land’, that is potentially suitable cropland which is not cultivated. The user can set the rate of these two factors to represent, respectively: the prevention of cropland abandonment (e.g. through improved soil and water management, agroforestry etc), and the assisted regeneration of abandoned cropland or increased access to inputs that facilitates farmers to cultivate more of the land that is available to them.

The area of cropland expansion is then calculated with the formula:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cropland expansion [ha]} &= (\text{Area required} - \text{Existing cropland} + \text{Abandoned cropland}) \times (1 \\ &\quad - \text{Proportion of expansion occurring on underutilized land}) \end{aligned}$$

Wood removals due to charcoal production

Total demand for charcoal is calculated based on the use of traditional or improved efficiency charcoal stoves in urban and rural areas. The user sets the percentage of houses using each technology.

It is assumed that charcoal produced with sustainable forest management practices, such as an alternate coupes and shelterbelt strip system, leads to no deforestation. In contrast, it is assumed that charcoal produced from natural forest at levels exceeding the fraction of non-renewable biomass (fNRB) leads to ongoing deforestation, as the fNRB represents the fraction which is clear felled at a rate which exceeds natural regeneration.

The wood demand from natural forests is calculated based on user-defined levels of sustainable forest management for charcoal and the use of efficient kilns. The level of demand above the fNRB is calculated, followed by the forest area required to meet that demand based on the average biomass density of forests.

Finally, to avoid double counting, a portion of that area is subtracted representing the area that is subsequently used for agriculture. Satellite data analysis by Sedano et al, 2024 indicated this to be 20% of the land cleared for charcoal (within 7 years). It is assumed the rest does not regenerate to close to its natural state due to climatic conditions and fires, and is therefore assumed to be cleared due to charcoal.

It is assumed the kiln efficiencies, the subsequent use of cleared land for agriculture, and the fNRB and are the same across scenarios, but they set as a user input because there is uncertainty over the typical values. For example, for the efficiency of traditional charcoal kilns in Zambia, reports cite variously: ~23% (WISDOM, which says "The total consumption of charcoal is estimated at 1.15 million tons, corresponds to 5 million tons of wood (DM)", 8-12% (Energypedia), 10-20% (GRZ, 2017), 25% (A2C, 2021). The fNRB is assumed this is 0.3 (A2C, 2021).

By setting the various user inputs, the user can explore the impact of changing household use of charcoal, increased sustainable forest management practices, increased use of efficient kilns or more co-ordinated planning of charcoal production alongside agricultural activities.

Regeneration of abandoned cropland

The areas of land undergoing other land cover conversions are set by the user directly as hectares per year, rather than via drivers. By increasing the rate of conversion from cropland to either grassland or forest, the user can represent increased assisted regeneration of those abandoned cultivated areas back to natural habitats. When cropland is abandoned, these processes might occur consecutively – i.e. cropland turning to grassland then tree cover developing– or with trees growing and forest developing directly, depending on the previous agriculture practices, and the agroecological conditions.

Other regeneration and conversion

Five further land cover transitions are shown in the historic data presented by Phiri et al. (2023). The user can represent other afforestation or reforestation by raising the rate of the grassland to forest conversion, or the rate of wetland regeneration by raising the rate of grassland to wetland. The conversions of settlement to forest and settlement to forest are expected to occur when settlements are abandoned so raising the rates of these could represent assisted regeneration.

Compilation of land cover change projections

As illustrated in Figure 3, associated with each of the first three land-use change processes, is an assumption about the specific land cover change that occurs when each process happens. These are derived from the historic data presented by Phiri et al. (2023).

SI.4 - Model drivers for illustrative results

Table SI.4 User inputs for the Reference and two illustrative scenarios (Note, 2030 values are also specified by the user in the tool)

	Base Year 2018	2050 values		
		Reference	“Low land cover change”	“High land cover change”
Expansion of settlements				
Urban population share				
Urban population density				
Crop demands				
Population	17.9 million	World Bank projection reaches 38.1 million		
Per capita demands	Calculated for each crop group	Constant for all years and scenarios		
Bioethanol blending	0	0	0	10% with cassava
Biodiesel blending	0	0	0	5% with soybeans
Crop yields				
Yields for each crop group	Average of historic yields 2016-2020	No change in yields since 2018	Yields (except sugar cane) increase by 30%	Yields decrease by 30%
Annual cropland abandonment [ha/yr]	88,000	88,000	79,200	96,800
Portion of cropland expansion that uses previously 'underutilized land' [%]	0	0	5	0
Portion of houses using charcoal as their main fuel				
Urban - trad stoves	60%	60%	30%	60%
Urban - ICS	5%	5%	5%	5%
Rural - trad stoves	15%	15%	0%	15%
Rural - ICS	0%	0%	0%	0%
Charcoal production				
Percentage of charcoal that is produced with sustainable forest management	0%	0%	20%	0%
Percentage of the charcoal from natural forest that is produced with efficient kilns	0%	0%	20%	0%
Regeneration of abandoned cropland (annual area converted)				
From cropland to forest [ha]	22,666	22,666	24,933	22,666
From cropland to grassland [ha]	13,892	13,892	15,281	13,892
Regeneration/conversion of other land types (annual area converted)				
Grassland to forest	1,828	1,828	2,011	1,829
Grassland to Wetland			Same as the base year	
Wetland to Grassland			Same as the base year	
Settlement to Forest			Same as the base year	
Settlement to Grassland			Same as the base year	